

Deliverable D8.9

Distributed analysis and federated learning PoC

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Date	Mvm	Who	Description
25/06/2023	V0.1	Carles Hernandez-Ferrer	Outline of the content agreed with WP, pillar leads, and contributors
09/07/2025	V0.2	Vojtech Bystry, Eugenio Gonzalo, Carles Hernandez-Ferrer	Updated description of the demonstrator and adding screenshots + detailed fragment descriptions to support the video.
04/08/2025	v0.3	Carles Hernandez-Ferrer	Reviewers' comments addressed
08/08/2025	V1.0	Ellie Younger	Final version submitted

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the design, implementation, and testing of a demonstrator for federated analysis within the European Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) project. It showcases a practical execution of a privacy-preserving Genome-Wide Association Study using a distributed architecture. Each participating national node (CZ, DE, PT, ES, SI, FI, EE) ran analyses locally, preserving data sovereignty and complying with legal constraints such as the GDPR. This demonstrator was built upon prior strategic and technical evaluations (previous deliverables and discussion from both WP7 and WP8) of federated technologies, validating the technical feasibility of GA4GH-compliant TES workflows. It leverages tools such as Snakemake, Docker, and MinIO, with Funnel serving as the TES endpoint. This prototype, using synthetic¹ data previously distributed across the national nodes and generated for this demonstrator, paves the way for federated learning and cross-border analytics at scale.

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

	Contributed
<p>Outcome 1</p> <p>Secure federated infrastructure and data governance needed to enable sustainable and secure cross border linkage of genomic data sets in compliance with the relevant and agreed legal, ethical, quality and interoperability requirements and standards based on the progress achieved by the 1+MG initiative.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 2</p> <p>Platform performing distributed analysis of genetic/genomic data and any linked clinical/phenotypic information; it should be based on the principle of federated access to data sources, include a federated/multi party authorisation and authentication system, and enable application of appropriate secure multi-party and/or high-end computing, AI and simulation techniques and resources.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 3</p> <p>Clear description of the roles and responsibilities related to personal data and privacy protection, for humans and computers, applicable during project lifetime and after its finalisation.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 4</p>	No

¹ `synthetic_input_data`

Business model including an uptake strategy explaining the motivation, patient incentives and conditions for all stakeholders at the different levels (national, European, global) to support the GDI towards its sustainability, including data controllers, patients, citizens, data users, service providers (e.g., IT and biotech companies), healthcare systems and public authorities at large.	
Outcome 5 Sustained coordination mechanism for the GDI and for the GoE multi-country project launched in the context of the 1+MG initiative.	Yes
Outcome 6 Communication strategy – to be designed and implemented at the European and national levels.	No
Outcome 7 Capacity building measures necessary to ensure the establishment, sustainable operation, and successful uptake of the infrastructure.	Yes
Outcome 8 Financial support to the relevant stakeholders to enable extension, upgrade, creation and/or physical connection of further data sources beyond the project consortium or to implement the communication strategy and for capacity-building.	No

3. Scope of the deliverable

This document outlines the motivation, context, and technical execution of a federated analysis demonstrator implemented as part of the collaboration between Pillar II and Pillar III of the GDI project, with an initial strategic leadership of WP8. It focuses on the federated access and execution of genomic analysis workflows, particularly Genome-Wide Association Study (GWAS), and sets the stage for future applications involving federated learning.

4. Introduction

4.1 Federated Analysis and Federated Learning

Federated approaches let algorithms travel to the data instead of moving data to a central server. That architectural choice alone does not ensure privacy. After local computation, intermediate statistics or model updates still have to leave the data holder, and without safeguards they can leak sensitive information. Techniques such as secure multi-party aggregation, homomorphic encryption, and differential privacy must therefore protect each transfer—from local node to aggregator and

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from aggregator to end user. When these safeguards are in place, federated learning can maintain data ownership at the source and deliver stronger privacy guarantees than traditional centralised analysis.

Figure 1. Simplification of the common area and specific areas of action between federated analysis and federated learning, depicted as a Venn diagram.

GDI intends to manage sensitive genomic and phenotypic data distributed across national boundaries. Transferring such data to a central location is both technically burdensome and legally restricted.

Federated analysis may become a key component for the GDI framework and environment because it can, if implemented correctly, provide:

- **Compliance** with EU and national regulations (e.g., GDPR and country-specific legislation)
- **Protection of sensitive data**, as analyses are conducted locally without exposing raw datasets
- **Scalability and reproducibility** across heterogeneous infrastructures through standardised algorithms and workflows
- **Alignment with national data governance policies**

Prior to this demonstrator, Pillar III conducted a benchmarking study of existing technologies for federated computation. While Galaxy offers a powerful workflow engine, it is not inherently federated. DataSHIELD supports statistical federation but lacks workflow orchestration, while Flower

is designed for federated learning but not general analytical pipelines². None of these platforms provided a unified framework for both analysis and learning.

This gap motivated the exploration of an alternative technological stack capable of supporting federated execution of general analytical workflows and thus support federated learning. The demonstrator described here adopts a combination of GA4GH TES + Snakemake, offering a lightweight, modular, and reproducible architecture for distributed genomic analysis.

5. The Demonstrator

5.1 Goal and Analytical Workflow

The goal was to run a federated GWAS using a standardised Snakemake workflow across multiple national nodes. Each node exposes a public TES endpoint via Funnel, receiving job requests that trigger local execution. Input VCFs with assigned binary phenotypes were stored in S3-compatible MinIO buckets. The orchestrating node collected the summary statistics (e.g., p-values, effect sizes) from each node and performed meta-analysis using METAL.

5.2 Participants (national nodes)

Participating teams of the demonstrator with the Czech Republic as technical lead:

National Node	Representative	Contact
Czech Republic	Vojtech Bystry	vojtech.bystry@ceitec.muni.cz
Germany	Luiz Gadelha	luiz.gadelha@dkfz-heidelberg.de
Portugal	Jorge Oliveira	jorge.oliveira@tecnico.ulisboa.pt
Spain	Eugenio Gonzalo	eugenio.gonzalo@bsc.es
Slovenia	Aleš Čep	ales.cep@um.si
Finland	Álvaro González	alvaro.gonzalez@csc.fi
Estonia	Priit Kleemann	priit.kleemann@ut.ee

² <https://zenodo.org/records/10887366>

5.3 Technology and Architecture

The architecture ensures full separation between data and workflow origin, relying on each node's compute infrastructure for the execution and results aggregation.

- **Funnel**³: Each node runs a GA4GH-compliant TES endpoint.
- **Snakemake**⁴: Used for defining and executing the GWAS workflow.
- **Docker**⁵: Used to containerise the pipeline ([krkoo/gwas-demo:2025-05-29](https://github.com/krkoo/gwas-demo) ⁶).
- **MinIO**⁷: Local S3-compatible storage for both input and output data.
- **SeqUla Portal**⁸: Graphical User Interface for dispatching and monitoring jobs.
- **LS AAI**⁹: Authentication infrastructure. For the demo, some endpoints were unauthenticated although, for any test or production environment, proper authentication and authorization is mandatory.

Technical Requirements:

- Public TES endpoint (internet-accessible)
- Local execution within each node (HPC or TRE if possible, otherwise compatible infrastructure)
- Access to MinIO-compatible S3 storage
- Outgress endpoints for result retrieval
- Shared registry access for pulling Docker images or local Docker image repository

³ Funnel at github: <https://github.com/CERIT-SC/funnel-gdi>

⁴ Snakemake at Read The Docs: <https://snakemake.readthedocs.io>

⁵ Docker web page: <https://www.docker.com/>

⁶ URL for the docker image with the GWAS pipeline used in the demonstrator: <https://hub.docker.com/r/krkoo/gwas-demo/tags> (tag: 2025-06-16)

⁷ MinIO web page: <https://min.io>

⁸ Login page to SeqUla: <https://devapp.sequia.eu>

⁹ Service for LS AAI: <https://services.aai.lifescience-ri.eu>

6. Results

We provide both a video and a series of screenshots showcasing the successful end-to-end execution of federated GWAS across the participating national nodes, orchestrated from the Czech node.

Figure 2. Name and short description of the seven steps of the demonstrator.

 Video recording of the demonstrator: [video1841278489.mp4](#)

Because the video is not a professional showcase of the demonstrator, we have included a series of screenshots that highlight its incomplete or less-detailed scenes. Nevertheless, a video showcasing the demonstrator will be redone and provided at a later date.

- Configuration of an analytical workflow in SeqUla portal - Parameter selection

This is the analytical workflow set-up page in SeqUla portal, where the different parameters of the software can be set up before running the federated analysis.

- Configuration of an analytical workflow in SeqUla portal - Selection of datasets to be used in the analytical workflow

The screenshot shows the SeqUla portal interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for Sequencing kits, Index kits, Samples, Libraries, Runs, Projects, Patients, Analysis, Tasks, Users, Groups, Sequencers, Workflows, Help, and Logout. Below the navigation bar is a 'Save' button and a text input field containing 'Save and launch project analysis'. The main content area is divided into two sections: 'Samples' and 'Tasks'.

Samples

select all select not analysed

Sample name	Library	Run name
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CZE_GDI_GWAS_res	New GWAS_fed_comp...	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> GER_GDI_GWAS_res	New GWAS_fed_comp...	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ESP_GDI_GWAS_res	New GWAS_fed_comp...	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SVN_GDI_GWAS_res	New GWAS_fed_comp...	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PRT_GDI_GWAS_res	New GWAS_fed_comp...	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EST_GDI_GWAS_res	New GWAS_fed_comp...	

Tasks

#	Workflow name	Workflow version	Created	Updated	Run by	Actual	Status	Action
50874	gwas_aggregation	dev_snakemake	2025-06-20 13:41	2025-06-20 13:42	Bystrý Vojtěch	Yes	Success	

(Items: 1 - 1 from 1)

This is the analytical workflow set-up page in SeqUla portal, where the datasets available to the user are displayed. The user can select which of them are to be used in the current analytical workflow. In the showcased page, the user has only access to the datasets for the demonstrator, one in each of the national nodes participating in the demonstrator.

- Job petition received to the participating national nodes though the Funnel TES endpoint.

```
{
  "err": null,
  "level": "debug",
  "msg": "responding: /tes.TaskService/CreateTask",
  "ns": "server",
  "resp": {
    "id": "d1akfn4hem4s73bvfrkd",
    "time": "2025-06-20T11:36:56Z"
  }
}
```

Log from the Funnel API deployed at the Spanish node. Highlighted in white the ID of the TES request can be seen; this ID will be used as the traceID during the whole execution flow to identify all messages, steps and outputs.

- The data used was synthetic and randomised to preserve privacy.

```
{
  "level": "debug",
  "msg": "received: /tes.TaskService/CreateTask",
  "ns": "server",
  "request": {
    "description": "GWAS Demo",
    "executors": [
      {
        "command": "snakemake",
        "noLock": true,
        "j2": true,
        "configFile": "/workflow/config.json",
        "showFailedLogs": true,
        "image": "krkoog/was-demo:2025-06-16"
      }
    ],
    "id": "9c1c02f6-de08-4369-94db-7f9397980f5c",
    "inputs": [
      {
        "path": "/germline_varcalls/SPADISEASE1.g.vcf.gz",
        "url": "s3://funnel/SPA_simulated_data/SPADISEASE1.g.vcf.gz"
      },
      {
        "path": "/germline_varcalls/SPADISEASE2.g.vcf.gz",
        "url": "s3://funnel/SPA_simulated_data/SPADISEASE2.g.vcf.gz"
      },
      {
        "path": "/germline_varcalls/SPADISEASE3.g.vcf.gz",
        "url": "s3://funnel/SPA_simulated_data/SPADISEASE3.g.vcf.gz"
      },
      {
        "path": "/germline_varcalls/SPADISEASE4.g.vcf.gz",
        "url": "s3://funnel/SPA_simulated_data/SPADISEASE4.g.vcf.gz"
      },
      {
        "path": "/germline_varcalls/SPADISEASE5.g.vcf.gz",
        "url": "s3://funnel/SPA_simulated_data/SPADISEASE5.g.vcf.gz"
      },
      {
        "path": "/germline_varcalls/SPADISEASE6.g.vcf.gz",
        "url": "s3://funnel/SPA_simulated_data/SPADISEASE6.g.vcf.gz"
      }
    ]
  }
}
```

TES requests input and run fields. TES request run field showing specifically what commands, parameters and which image will be used for this specific task. Input field, not shown fully due to its length, contains a list of all the input objects involved in the workflow run; each input object contains both the path and url of the requested input file.

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```
337a-41d5-9fe4-1cd4a318e4f9", "outputs": [{"path": "/workflow/association_results/manhattan_plot.pdf", "url": "s3://funnel/gwas-results/9c1c62f6-de60-4369-94db-7f9397900f5c/manhattan_plot.pdf"}, {"path": "/workflow/association_results/association_results.assoc", "url": "s3://funnel/gwas-results/9c1c62f6-de60-4369-94db-7f9397900f5c/association_results.assoc"}], "time": "2025-06-20T11:36:56Z"}
```

TES request outputs fields. This small excerpt shows specifically the output field definition of the TES request, showing where the expected results of the workflow should be stored or its files be named

ID	State	Name	Created At	Elapsed Time
d1akfm4hem4s73bvfrkg	COMPLETE	95af0d3f-337a-41d5-9fe4-1cd4a318e4f9	--	
d1akdtchem4s73bvfrk0	COMPLETE	95af0d3f-337a-41d5-9fe4-1cd4a318e4f9	--	
d1akbt4hem4s73bvfrjg	COMPLETE	95af0d3f-337a-41d5-9fe4-1cd4a318e4f9	--	
d1ak9jkhem4s73bvfrj0	COMPLETE	95af0d3f-337a-41d5-9fe4-1cd4a318e4f9	--	

This is Funnel's UI where the list of received requests can be seen. Note that more executions were done in preparation for this demo (before the dry-run to test and accept the workflow). During the demonstrator session, the last request in purple was received and successfully executed and this request can be identified by the trace ID previously shown highlighted in the log's screenshot.

Task: d1akfm4hem4s73bvfrkg

TEXT	JSON
Name	95af0d3f-337a-41d5-9fe4-1cd4a318e4f9
ID	d1akfm4hem4s73bvfrkg
State	COMPLETE
Description	GWAS Demo

Funnel's UI excerpt of the request's detailed page, showing identifying info related to the task execution. The name will be used as the folder name that will contain execution's outputs.

Output File Log

path	/workflow/association_results/manhattan_plot.pdf
size_bytes	1071257
url	s3://funnel/gwas-results/9c1c62f6-de60-4369-94db-7f9397900f5c/manhattan_plot.pdf
path	/workflow/association_results/association_results.assoc
size_bytes	204794820
url	s3://funnel/gwas-results/9c1c62f6-de60-4369-94db-7f9397900f5c/association_results.assoc

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Funnel's UI excerpt of the request's detailed page, showing output info related to the task execution, matching previous screenshot info as was shown in the output parameter fields.

- Results of the local computation of the analytical workflow, ready to be outgressed and aggregated in the orchestration node - local-node S3 storages.

Name	Last Modified	Size
association_results.assoc	Fri, Jun 20 2025 13:37 (GMT+2)	195.3 MiB
manhattan_plot.pdf	Fri, Jun 20 2025 13:37 (GMT+2)	1.0 MiB

This is the content of the outgress folder on the MinIO for the Spanish national node. The results of the GWAS pipeline executed at the node's premises can be accessed and/or downloaded via an S3 connection.

- Status of an analytical workflow in SeqUla portal - Successful execution of the full analytical pipeline.

Project name	Group	Created	Samples	Analysis	Stages	Last analyzed stage	Last task workflow	Last task created	Status	Action
GDI_fed_comp_aggregation	CF Bioinformatics	2025-06-19	6	GWAS (aggregation)	1	aggregation_test	GWAS analysis aggregation (dev_snakemake)	2025-06-20 13:41	Analysis success	🔗 ⚙️
GDI_fed_comp_demo	CF Bioinformatics	2025-06-17	240	GWAS (GDI demo)	3	All_nodes_demonstrator	Genome-Wide Association Study (GWAS) Analysis (dev_snakemake)	2025-06-20 13:36	Analysis success	🔗 ⚙️

This is the main page of SeqUla where we can observe the successful execution of the analytical workflow. This analytical workflow was composed of two main stages: the GWAS run in each of the national nodes and an aggregation (metanalysis) run at the orchestrating node (CZ).

- Status of an analytical workflow in SeqUla portal - Results observation.

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Task report for the stage [aggregation_test \(GDI_fed_comp_aggregation\)](#) (for the task "gwas_aggregation") [download archive](#) [main report page](#)

Top 30 SNPs

The table below lists the top 30 SNPs based on the aggregated combined p-values. For each SNP, its chromosomal position is indicated, along with the $-\log_{10}$ transformed p-values from each individual dataset as well as the combined value. Missing values are represented by "-".

Top 30 SNPs ($-\log_{10}$ P-values)

CHR	BP	logP_combined_mean_P	logP_P_CZ	logP_P_EST	logP_P_GER	logP_P_POR	logP_P_SPA	logP_P_SVN
1	47144918	2.176	-	2.805	-	-	-	1.546
1	112918054	2.33	-	-	-	2.33	-	-
3	112041924	2.174	-	2.174	-	-	-	-

This is the main page of SeqUla where we can observe the successful execution of the analytical workflow. This analytical workflow was composed of two main stages: the GWAS run in each of the national nodes and an aggregation (metanalysis) run at the orchestrating node (CZ).

7. Impact and Next Steps

This demonstrator proves the viability of federated analysis across diverse European infrastructures (i.e. GDI's national nodes).

Moreover, the selected analytical workflow—a federated genome-wide association study (federated GWAS)—is of particular interest to WP7, since population-scale analytics are essential for its objectives. This includes specific cases such as the Genome of Europe initiative and analyses of common and complex diseases.

Key next steps include:

- Integrating LS AAI OIDC authentication with TES endpoints
- Study LS AAI capabilities to include user authorization to access file-in-dataset granularity
- Automating meta-analysis and result aggregation

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- Extending to real-world datasets in compliance with national laws
- Expanding workflows to support additional diseases and multi-omic data
- Exploring integration with Galaxy (via TES) for user-friendly WES pipelines and with Flower-like technologies for federated learning
- Standardising orchestration layers, currently based on SeqUIa

This work advances GDI's mission to establish a privacy-respecting, interoperable ecosystem for genomic analysis, ready to scale toward more complex federated analysis and learning use cases.

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